

Supporting Information for Commentary on Li and Aitken (2024): Antarctic geothermal heat; geology matters

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May 7, 2024, 2:18am

Distance distribution in compilations

The distribution of distances between samples in PetroChron (Sanchez et al., 2021), and the global compilation by Gard, Hasterok, and Halpin (2019a). In Antarctica, the continent's size limits the distribution's extent (a). The bulge on the Gard et al. (2019a) distribution is the trivial result of the spherical globe and distances between regions well studied (b).

Heat production distribution from compilations

The distribution of heat production computed in PetroChron (Sanchez et al., 2021), and the global compilation by Gard et al. (2019a). Only records used in this commentary are included.

Figures: Heat production vs. distance

The difference in calculated heat production is plotted versus the distance between records; here, it is presented on an extended axis (a and b) in relation to the figure in the main article (Fig. 1) and also as a zoom-in on the very nearest samples (c and d). The green background is a 2D histogram where each distance bin has been normalised for clarity. The actual distribution is shown in Fig. S1. The red markers indicate the median heat production for each distance bin. The investigation is derived and modified from Fig. S13. (Stål et al., 2021). The relation breaks at the highest separation bins due to very few samples being so far apart in Antarctica (a).

References Supplementary material

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